

Attending, Understanding, and Interpreting : Towards an Epistemology of the Middle English Dream Vision

ABSTRACT: With its roots in the writings of Augustine, the notion of ‘attention’ plays an important role not only in late medieval devotional culture and moral psychology, but also in medieval epistemology and philosophy of mind. Whether it is designated by the Latin term *intentio* or not, early authors from Boethius to Abelard already develop this notion, which achieves particular prominence as part of the ‘epistemic turn’ of Western philosophy from the thirteenth century onwards, in the wake of the wider circulation of Aristotle’s *De Anima* and associated commentaries. Strikingly, the notion of attention is invoked not only as part of the discussion of the mechanism of ordinary perception, but also plays an important role in medieval philosophers’ attempts to formulate theories of ‘mental language’, suggesting that cognitive processes behave in manner analogous to linguistic signification. The cognition of simple objects accordingly relies on *intentio* in a manner broadly analogous to the interpretation of linguistic propositions, and in both cases the agency of the individual subject plays a crucial role in enabling an adequate cognitive response. In this paper I propose an overview of such theories, with the aim of illustrating how such debates over the role of attention in medieval philosophy of mind resonate with the philosophical concerns that underpin much late medieval dream poetry: while such poetry is not, for the most part, directly influenced by the formal tools of medieval philosophy of mind, scholastic authors and poets can be seen to explore & set of common problems. These problems ultimately revolve around the philosophically central question of whether perception and thought are best considered passive experiences *of*, or active interventions *in*, the world mediated by our senses.

- I will talk of attention not so much in a primarily spiritual / devotional sense, but in a more strictly cognitive sense, such as it is theorized and conceptualized in Medieval Philosophy of Mind. Of course things are more complex – and more interesting - since medieval philosophy of mind (if the term has any use at all...) is not a self-contained and easily circumscribed “discipline”, but rather an area of intellectual speculation that is inextricably enmeshed with theology. Discussion of perception, mental faculties, and cognitive processes occurs not only in literature produced within the Arts Faculty at the late medieval University, but also constitutes an important strand within theological discussions, notably in Sentences commentaries (Brinzei recent...)¹ So my focus on the question of attention from an ontological and epistemic perspective is not meant to exclude theology or even religious practice, but is rather intended to highlight some epistemological problems that concern both secular and religious authors (again, this distinction is reductive... since the authors who are responsible for discussion of Natural sciences almost invariably produce theological discussion)

Attention and Intention

- *Intentio* in XIII-XIV scholastic philosophy of mind is, more often than not, a feature inherent in objects (and analogous in some respects to *species*), and not in the mental operations of the perceiver (Tachau – Intentional Existence at Paris). (*Q: to what extent is this kind of intentio compatible – or synonymous – with Augustine’s notion of Intentio? It feels completely different... so we need to disambiguate*)

¹ *Philosophical Psychology in Late-Medieval Commentaries on Peter Lombard’s Sentences*

- Auriol's separation of mental representation as such (the presence of species/imago...), which is inert, and the act of transferring the image into presence, into *esse apparens*, which is an intentional act (> Friedman in Klima). A great gloss on the inaugural image of BD....
- There appears to be a long tradition for thinking of mental operations as a form of 'mental language', where imaginative acts are analogous to dictions (Abelard; bacon on species; Auriol on *dictio* and 'reading' in Friedman in Klima).

Abelard (Rosier Article)

- Boethius' Rejection of the passive (stoic) theory of perception (broadly identical to the 'empirical' Aristotelian theory of perception, as popularised by the perspectivists in the West on the basis of the writings of Alhacen) >> Boece. Rosier 252
- Rosier on Abelard and *attentio*: moves away from a mimetic semantics (which Ab assigns to Boethius) towards an intentionalist semantics, which likewise presupposes an act of 'attending to' *significata* in order for adequate understanding to occur. Notion of 'discretio' in mental operations (253). This is not a power of the soul (passive, like sensation and imagination, which man shares with animals..), but an ACT of the understanding (so far Abelard seems to concur with Boethius); BUT Abelard then goes on to contradict Boethius on the point of the necessity of images to cause understanding...
- Abelard (Rosier 254) on the sense perception of a statue, which is either a thing in itself or a sign for the thing (Achilles in this case): to what extent is this echoed in the liminal imagery of Chaucer's dram poetry? Does it point to a shared semantic preoccupation?)
- Abelard denies that the intellect requires images to produce Understanding; crucially here he brings in the example of the student, apprehending not the things in front of them but the objects of their intellectual work . So he denies the causal link between sense perception and Understanding (254). (MN – I'm not sure the example really proves the point he makes – if this is indeed the point he does make...). On this account, images are 'distractions' of Understanding (!).
- For Ab, words signify not passions of the soul that stand for things (as for Boethius), but a range of understandings, both correct and erroneous ones (otherwise no words could be coined, and understood, for non-existent things that have not been experienced through the senses). Words stand for *intellectiones* - not for *passiones*.
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Thank you for the invitation!

Many of the contributions here focus on the role of attention in specifically religious, monastic, or devotional context. In my own paper I would like to take a broader, 'cognitive' approach to the question of attention. More specifically, I want to examine how the phenomenon of 'attention' is conceptualised in two areas: in medieval scholastic writings - and more specifically in relation to **both** philosophy of mind and philosophy of language; and in late medieval dream poetry (which may or may not be of a loosely 'religious' character).

This is a tricky exercise, and I fell down a number of rabbit holes, and encountered a number of substantial methodological challenges. This means that I am not ready - I think - to have a fully-fledged and clear 'argument' about the relationship between scholastic psychology and literary

expression (perhaps not surprisingly, given that this is a question that has often been tackled). Instead, I want to point to a number of 'resonances' between these two areas. 'Resonances' is a usefully evasive formulation, because it rather eschews (or 'dodges'..) the thorny question of 'influence'. Part of me would **like** to make an argument about the 'influence' of scholastic faculty psychology and *Sprachlogik* on poetry - arguing for instance that poets reflect on the experience of producing and consuming poetic texts (often figured as dreams, or framed by a dream) by using some of the tools, theories, and terminology that is 'borrowed' from medieval scholastic discussions of the powers of the soul, the mind, the imagination, and sense perception. I say that I would 'like to do this', because this would make my life much easier - and I would have a clear argument.

As things stand, however, I believe that the configuration is rather more complex: on the one hand, I believe that the wish to read literary texts as a simple 'implementations' of existing scholastic theories is quite flawed: vernacular literary texts are not bound by the same institutional, formal, and epistemic strictures as the scholastic literature produced within the Arts and Theology faculties of late medieval Europe, and they do not pursue the same objectives. Literary texts make no claim to 'scientific' rigour (*akribēia* or *exactitudo*), in terms determined by the widely accepted scholastic definitions of *scientia*, generally understood in its Aristotelian, or apodeictic sense, where science is what produces certainty by using the demonstrative syllogism (the key text here is Robert Grosseteste's commentary on the *Posterior Analytics*, from the 1220s). So in some sense I think we should accept that literary fiction - *fabula* or *poetrie* - does not make the same kinds of claims regarding the 'truth' of its propositions that we find in scholasticism.

This is not to say that literary texts - or poetry - is devoid of either philosophical value, or that it utterly disregards the question of the 'truthfulness' of its own formulations — or indeed that that literary production takes place in a sphere that is completely disconnected from that of the discussions that take place in the medieval Arts and Theology faculties...

. My point - rather - is that it is not only historically inaccurate to read literary texts only as simplified approximations or 'vernacular translations' of available, ready-made philosophical ideas. To read poetry in this way is intellectually and philosophically reductive. In fact, I am arguing that poetic writing of a certain kind (here dream vision poetry) is animated by an intrinsic and deeply philosophical aspiration of its own - which is different from that of scholasticism, and accordingly takes on very different textual forms from the latter while nonetheless remaining aware of the latter's existence - to some degree that is often very difficult to determine. In addition, there are at least some - fairly minimal it has to be said - points of contact between literary production and philosophical speculation in this period and in the corpus of texts I am interested in.

In the case of cognition, therefore, I think it is not - or not only - a matter of poets being 'inspired' or 'influenced' by the work of roughly contemporary scholastic authors (although there are some, but often rather occasional and clearly circumscribed points of contact'...), but more a matter of a natural affinity between poets and 'philosophers' (for want of a better word...) in terms of the deep, fundamental epistemological questions they confront. One area where this affinity or convergence is particularly strong - throughout history and not just in the middle ages - is **the age-old philosophical question of the relation between so-called 'reality' in the outside world, and our mental grasp of that reality**. This binary relation is made more complex - or more interesting - by the addition of a third term, namely that of language. What is the relation between words, real things, and the stuff that happens in our brains or imagination?

This is an age-old question that we still grapple with, but that in the Middle Ages was even more central than it is for us today. For our purposes, and in a historical perspective, the question is

usefully and influentially formulated by Aristotle, in a famous, seminal passage from the *Peri Hermeneias* - a passage that has been credited as the point of origin for the ENTIRE history of medieval theories of signification:²

Now spoken sounds are symbols of affections in the soul, and written marks symbols of spoken sounds. And just as written marks are not the same for all men, neither are spoken sounds. But what these are in the first place signs of—affections of the soul—are the same for all; and what these affections are likenesses of—actual things—are also the same. These matters have been discussed in the work on the soul and do not belong to the present subject [cf. *De Anima* III.5–8]

So these are age-old questions, but as many of you know they acquire a new prominence from the early xiii century onwards, with the rediscovery of Aristotle's complete organon, and especially his works on the human soul - the *De anima* - and natural philosophy. These matters are absolutely at the heart of nearly all developments in western scholasticism over two centuries, from about 1200 to 1400 - both in philosophy of mind (or faculty psychology) and in philosophy of language (Grammar and Logic, and specifically semantics). It is quite simply unimaginable that any literate person with sufficient knowledge to produce the kinds of literary works we now consider canonical in fourteenth-century French and English literature (say Machaut, Froissart, Deschamps, Chaucer, Langland, Gower) would not be aware of these debates in a broad sense and to some degree. And you will notice how here I am trying to bring back in - through the back door as it were... - the intractable bugbear of 'influence' - but I also try to interrogate and complicate what we might exactly mean by that term, which seems to me to cover a potentially huge and bewildering range of very different types of relationships. We can come back to that if you like during questions...

Now, I move finally to 'attention', and to the start of the actual paper, and to some sort of tentative 'argument'. In what follows I will be talking primarily about the work of scholastic authors, but I will do in the hope that the very general, and brutally selective overview I provide can shed some light on what happens in some medieval dream poetry. More specifically, I want to suggest that collectively, scholastic discussions of *attentio* can serve as a gloss on one of the central preoccupations that traverses the literary genre of the late medieval dream vision as a whole : this preoccupation is structured as a three-step process; the first step consists of **two types of 'input'** (sensory experience and the reading of texts - or if you will 'experience' and auctoritee'; the second step is **the 'elaboration' of these inputs** in the mind, through the faculty of the imagination; and the third and final step is selection and organisation of these 'things in the mind' that finally produce **the 'articulation' of individual subjectivity** through a poetic language (Dream vision poems are almost invariably 'first-person narratives'). This configuration - in some very general but also very profound sense - reproduces the triangular configuration of Aristotle's semantic triangle: the outside world mediated by the senses - or by words; the conceptual constructs we produce in our mind to represent that outside world; and the language we use in order to position ourselves (as individual agents and/or subjects) in relation to both the world and our mind/imagination, and to 'communicate' - for better or for worse - our understanding of our own individual positioning in relation to both the mind and the world...

² 'the medieval debate on signification can be regarded as a commentary on these few lines', Giorgio Pini, 'Species, Concept and Thing: Theories of Signification in the Second Half of the Thirteenth Century', *Medieval Philosophy & Theology* 8.1 (1999), 21–52 (22). See also Norman Kretzmann, 'Aristotle on Spoken Sounds Significant by Convention', in J. Corcoran, ed., *Ancient Logic and its Modern Interpretations* (Dordrecht: Reidel, 1974), pp. 3–21.

This 'triangular' configuration is particularly prominent during some key 'liminal or inaugural moments' in dream vision poems — and in particular in Dream-poems written by Chaucer. So in some ways the following paper only works if you are familiar with the materials to some degree. I have provided the citation for some of the passages themselves in the handout, so we can perhaps pick them apart together during the discussion - but I will not be reading those out.

Now, some highly general considerations about these quite striking passages before I turn to the scholastics. All passages describe what could be called a 'liminal', 'incipient' or 'transitional' moment of poetic vision: by this I mean that they describe a moment where the imagination of the dreamer undergoes some major reorientation - either from rest to action, or vice-versa, or the transition from one 'state' of dreaming/awareness to another. The dreamer is - more often than not - confronted with a mixture of texts and images (so verbal and visual - a detail that is a pretty important detail for my argument...), generally through the mediating power of memory/recollection; and it is as a consequence of that encounter between the first-person subject/dreamer/poet/narrator figure and the information thus retrieved and re-presented, the dreamer moves into the core of the dream/poem, into its most personal and in some sense 'intimate' space, where the actual action unfolds.

So it is often at this particular juncture in each dream poem that we move from a familiar space populated by relatively disorganised, and often overwhelming reminiscences of objects, places, texts, and poetic conventions that exist in the 'outside world', into the actual vision which is particular to the individual subject writing the poem, and which consists in the dreamer / narrator tracing some sort of active path through this very cluttered world... by means of a journey recorded in a first-person narrative that is recorded in poetic writing (language). To use Chaucer's own terms from the *House of Fame*, this is where we move from the reacquaintance with familiar, pre-existing 'places' (*topoi* - both visual/sensory and textual) stored in the memory and brought into play by the imagination, to the discovery and exploration of 'sum newe thyng' - that is, to the writing of a new poem.

My working hypothesis is that it is precisely in these inaugural moments that poets are reflecting on the relation between things, words, and mental processes, as well as reflecting on the status of their own poetic craft. More specifically, I suggest that poets conceptualise the cognition of images or other objects of sensory perception — especially 'sounds' (birdsong) or more rarely 'smell' > flower in PF (...*but the margerite is also an intertextual reference*)— in ways that are broadly analogous to the manner in which they understand the cognitive processing of linguistic utterances, and specifically the interpretation of earlier poetic texts or fragments thereof. **So essentially I postulate a broad analogy between sense perception and literary reception**, and want to suggest that in both cases **attention** plays an important role in enabling an 'adequate understanding' of these two types of phenomena, i.e. sensory information and linguistic utterances. I'm also suggesting that this is something poets have in common with a number of scholastic thinkers - who similarly perceive AND THEORISE broad underlying analogies between the mechanisms of sense perception and linguistic interpretation, although these parallels are often developed in rather divergent ways by various thinkers. In both cases - for the poets and the philosophers - the notion of **attention** often plays a key role in these two cognitive processes, and it is only through an adequately focused attention that a 'sound understanding' can emerge - an idea to which I will return at the end

So, let me review the thought of some philosophers here... I've organised this 'by the kilo' so we can really just stop whenever you've had enough (!). Not all authors use the term *attentio* when speaking about what we would recognise as 'attention', but many of them do.

Abelard

the earliest thinker I want to discuss is Abelard - not because he influenced later developments, but because he seems to anticipate those later debates in striking manner, and because his own ideas on the topic really are very illuminating I think.

Abelard's problem is - very broadly speaking - that the Aristotelian theory of knowledge (as described by Boethius in his Second commentary on the *Peri hermeneias*), is strongly 'deterministic', in the sense that it emphasises the **central role of images** in the operation of the intellect. The imagination is essentially a NECESSARY but largely **passive** intermediary between the sense and the intellect. You are all familiar with the Aristotelian dictum that 'the mind never thinks without an image' - ('nihil intelligit sine phantasmate anima' cf. *De anima* III.7, 431a16–17). The problem with this idea - especially if paired with another familiar Aristotelian notion, that 'nothing comes to be in the mind that was not previously in the senses' ('Nihil est in intellectu quod non prius fuerit in sensu', cf. e.g. Aquinas, *Quaestiones disputatae de veritate*, q. 2, a. 3 ad 19 - is that this seems to entail an overwhelmingly **passive** theory of knowledge. And this is a problem that successive generations of philosophers will have to deal with, from Boethius himself right to the XIV century... (> article by Tachau, 'Approaching', p. 13)

vision have and must be navigated. The greater the activity of the world upon the observer, the more reason we have to worry that the universe is a deterministic one; the greater the activity of the observer's eye and brain in representing the world to the mind, the more reason we have to worry that these representations are sufficiently arbitrary and unique to misrepresent the world or represent it incompletely²⁴. Worse, these may

So, it's worth stressing that Abelard's discussion of this problem begins with Boethius's second commentary on Aristotle's *Peri hermeneias* (the semantic triangle we looked at before...), where Boethius broadly endorses this idea. But Boethius also strongly qualifies this notion, and indeed finally rejects the idea of an entirely passive and image-dependent cognition in a really important passage of the *Consolation of Philosophy*, where he denounces the 'Stoic' theory of perception — precisely because it is deterministic, and makes the immaterial rational intellect dependent on the imagination, whose objects are material in origin... being mediated by the senses. I have given you Chaucer's translation of this passage from the *Boece* - one fairly incontestable point of 'influence' I would say...

For Boethius this is a problem because it would mean that the operation of the immaterial intellect is effectively determined by the action of material objects upon it - which makes the intellect - the highest portion of the human *mens*, that is the immortal intellectual soul, made in the image of God — a purely passive faculty.

Boethius's 'corrects' this view by arguing for the **action** of the intellect, through its own forms, upon the residual 'marks' (*notae*) that the imagination has abstracted from the senses - but for Abelard this does not quite do the trick. And **so Abelard introduces the notion of *attentio*** in order to provide a fuller, more detailed description of the operation of the intellect, and develop Boethius's point in the *Consolation*.

(he also argues that the objects of the imagination are the products not of sensory perception, but of the intellect itself... but that is relatively unimportant for us here.)

The central idea here is that for Abelard the Imagination produces a 'confused' image of its objects, where the multiple qualities or properties of the object are as it were 'disorganised' (LAT? *permixta*); it is precisely by applying *attentio* that the intellect is then able to discriminate and differentiate (*discretio*) between these different properties, and able to **attend to** a limited, specific number of the object's properties, usually only a handful at any given time - or indeed attend to separate properties of objects that are originally separate, and to combine or 'confect' these (*conficit*) — the typical example being the 'chimera' (a Lion-Goat-Fish assemblage), or a white raven, or a rational raven.

~~Crucially, then, it is totally possible to attend to an object's properties in ways that are inadequate, and in ways that produce an understanding that is *untrue*. That is not a case of error however, because the element that determines erroneousness is not the act of the intellect, but the assent or belief (*assentire*).~~

What is most striking to me, however, is that by introducing the concept of *attentio* as a key element of the perceptual process - in order to defend the idea of an active cognition by the intellect - he also creates the spaces for the multiplication of different acts of understanding. Crudely put, there is no single way of understanding an object because there are potentially infinite ways of *attending* to it. Different perceivers may understand (*intelligere*) the same object in the same moment in completely different ways - and even my own *intellectio* of an object can vary dramatically from one instance - or instant - to another.

It may be because of the notion of the 'rational raven' or the 'white raven' — but I couldn't help being reminded of a Wallace Steven Poem "**Thirteen ways of looking at a blackbird**". Except that we are talking about the xii century..

Now, what is striking about Abelard's notion of *attentio*, is that he also mobilises it as part of his discussion of language, which we find in a set of very different writings on Logic. The process through which we understand individual words and more complex propositions is largely analogous to the way we understand objects of the imagination. For Abelard words have a twofold signifying operation: they signify things themselves (*significatio rerum*) when those things are present, and they signify particular understandings of objects (*significatio intellectum*). Crucially, the 'understandings' that are signified are not really 'images': they are produced by acts of the intellect. This is why "Abelard always reinterprets Boethius' definition of words as representing "*passiones animae*" (cf. triangle in *De Int.* 16^a7–8) as instances "*intellectus*," claiming that they are not formed as passive impressions and likenesses of the things, but through a particular act of the intellect that attends to such things" (Irene p. 258). Again, the reason for this is that words can signify non-existent things: words stand for fictitious understandings as well as understandings that are sound and accurate/adequate. This matters because it is clearly possible to signify understandings that have no corresponding *res subiecta* or object in the real world - the typical example being the signification of common names, such as 'man' in the sense of 'mankind' (*homo*), but any other common name will do - 'tree' or 'house': we understand those words even though we have never encountered those concepts as real entities (only particular instances of those concepts), and therefore cannot form 'images' of them, but only 'understandings' (*intellectiones*). This is of course a typical manifestation of Abelard's 'nominalism' or 'conceptualism' to be more accurate...

Now, while proper names (say 'Socrates') generate 'singular' understandings, common names generate a "common and confused image of many," a "confused" understanding, that is to say an indeterminate one, but which can apply to any" members of that 'class' (Irene 263). " This means that in practice the act of 'confused' understanding needs to be organised by an act of

'abstraction', that is by "separating forms that really exist as united (*permixta*)" - and this is of course where Abelard again brings in the term *attentio*. Again, different acts of *attentio* will result in the mind or intellect 'attending' to different aspects or qualities of a word's *significatio intellectum*.

These difficulties pertain to individual words or *dictiones*, and are of course exacerbated when we are talking about complex propositions. Developing the notion of attention a little further still, Abelard makes what I think is a really fascinating point about propositions — namely that propositions are just that: '*pro-positiones*' the 'pro-*pose*', they 'offer to our consideration', they 'suggest a range of understandings' as it were, through a certain configuration of words in a sentence — but again the formulation of a particular **understanding** on the basis of any '*pro-positio*' requires the exercise of *attentio* that characterises the intellectual act, re-organising and selecting specific qualities that characterise a word's *significatio intellectum*.

Once more - just as in the perceptual act - the central, and active role of *attentio* in the process of decrypting the meaning of complex propositions (as well as individual words) means that we introduce the possibility of nearly endless divergence in understanding a single proposition: it is less a question of erroneous understanding of a proposition (that is again the function of whether we *assent* to the act of the intellect or do not..), and more a case of creating a potentially endless number of different ways of attending to the content of a single object / word / proposition. There are, it seems, as many ways of 'attending to' - or decomposing, understanding, or organising an utterance as there are listeners or instances of communication... but conversely this means that single propositions (and let alone extended texts) never have a single and fixed meaning. This creates almost endless opportunities for miscommunication and misunderstanding.

Again: 'Thirteen ways of understanding the word 'blackbird' - or indeed, an infinite number of possible ways in which we could approach, and understand, a poem such as 'thirteen ways of looking at a blackbird'.

~~Now, as a non-specialist I am tempted to use the word 'scepticism' to describe the implications of this kind of theory - but of course 'scepticism' in the strict, medieval sense, is something far more radical. So we can think of other words to describe such a theory - perhaps relativistic, positional, subjectivistic, or perspectival...~~

What matters more to me in the present context is that later medieval theories of cognition — while often built on rather different foundations than Abelard's theory — end up having to confront the same problem of the role of agency, and particularly the role of attention in the perceptual act. Many of the key thinkers in these developments are indeed English, writing between about 1320 and 1340 in and around Oxford.

The key dispute concerned nothing less than the question of the 'object' of knowledge: what is, ultimately, the 'thing' that is known through a cognitive act? Do humans know particular, natural, and contingent objects in the physical world (Peter John Olivi); an intentional and purely conceptual *verbum* (Thomas Aquinas); the propositions themselves as constituted by linguistic or mental objects (William of Ockham and Robert Holcot); or the notorious *complexe significabile*, i.e. an abstract but extra-mental entity signified by linguistic constructs (Adam of Wodeham and Gregory of Rimini)?

And more importantly: what is our role or perhaps our choice and our 'responsibility' - as individual agents - in shaping this process, in performing it adequately? Do we indeed

have any 'room' as it were to act, or to 'attend' to different qualities or aspects of a particular object, or word, or complex proposition?

A key stage of the development is the introduction of the so-called *species* theory, propounded by Albert the Great and especially Roger Bacon in the West, on the basis of the writings of the 'perspectivists' - that is primarily Alhacen and Avicenna. More importantly perhaps, late medieval poets appear to have been aware of these later theories and debates, at least to a minimal degree - I have given you a passage from a speech by Jean de Meun's lady Nature in the *Roman de la Rose* (the bestseller of all bestsellers), on the refractive properties of mirrors, which is essentially a verbatim translation of Bacon's *perspectiva* into French. One particularly striking thing to me is that in Bacon's example he talks about the ability of mirrors to enlarge minuscule objects - and particularly its ability to enlarge TEXT, 'tiny letters' - and this again associates sense perception with the decoding of language...

Now species-theory is strongly 'intromissionist' and postulates the existence of a sensible *species* in the medium acting upon the sense organs—and even though Bacon comes up with some acrobatic and quite unconvincing attempts to preserve at least some degree of agency for the intellect, many contemporaries found the theory to be problematic, since it leaves little room to the agency of the individual Will. Peter of John Olivi, for one, rejects the agency of species entirely, precisely on this ground, and proposes a very different theory of the soul's action upon the objects of cognition in the external world, imagined as a cognitive 'reaching out' and 'acting upon' its objects. The reason for this is precisely the need to avoid a 'deterministic' universe where the human soul becomes a passive object of the actions of external, material objects. This theory is - I think - behind a rather extraordinary passage in Guillaume de Deguileville's *Pèlerinage de Vie Humaine* - a widely circulated text familiar to both Chaucer and William Langland, and that circulated widely in Europe.

There are numerous later theories that address aspects of this problem - many of these cluster around the question of the role of *intentiones* in the perceptual act - and the nature of such *intentiones* were defined in radically different ways by different authors. It is worth stressing that the term *intentio* no longer occurs in these later theories as it did with Abelard - but the core of the problem remains the same, in the sense that the debate concerns the nature and the role of the cognitive ACT carried out by the perceiver in relation to the object known, and the underlying question of *where and how exactly that act is directed*.

(((((((((((It is worth stressing that *intentio* does not - at least initially - designate a strictly mental or imaginative entity: for Avicenna and Alhacen it designates a diminished, non-material, but clearly real existence (Scots and Durandus of St Pourçain are the first to differentiate between the two, potentially contradictory meaning of *esse intentionale...*, the first in the strict sense of 'mental reality', and the second as a real entity of diminished being..). The concept of *intentiones* was invoked to get around the unresolved question of the ontological status of the *species* - which clearly was not quite that of a material image or representation, but nonetheless a manifestation of the nature of the object known without its material accidents. Scotus and his generation essentially accepted Bacon's idea that the notoriously problematic *species* had 'intentional being', and thus amounted to an entity that was identical to the object, but where that object's nature was, as it were 'diminished', and thus not material (but nonetheless *real*). In order to avoid the charge of 'representationalism' (i.e. the idea that what we perceive is not the object itself but only its 'representation'...) some thinkers clarified that the species was the *means* and not the *object* of the perceptual act.)))))))

Peter Aureol, in 1320 Paris reintroduces the possibility that the act of cognition might not focus on the object by means of the *species* that has been reliably abstracted from that object at all.... For Aureol the object of knowledge is of the elusive *esse apparens* - an apparent being that may or *may not* accurately 'correspond' to external objects, and that has been produced not by the object itself, but by the act of perception carried out by the perceiver's mind. In fact, for Aureol, the perceiver apprehends two objects: the thing itself (which in some sense **causes** the act of perception) and its apparent being (which is **produced by** the act of perception).

To make things more complex, Aureol also designates this *esse apparens* as an *esse intentionale* - and this means that he completely transforms the meaning of *intentiones*: for him intentions are mental entities and no longer real ones - although arguably he is not entirely consistent on this point... So *esse apparens* and *esse intentionale* are interchangeable terms in Aureol's vocabulary. They are essentially 'concepts', and another term that Aureol also uses for this new entity, is *verbum mentale*. And this is where the strictly intellectual ACT kicks in (Tachau book 103): on the basis of first intentions - or first-order concepts, which are mental propositions - the intellect determines the truthfulness or accuracy of the concept itself in relation to the object: this allows the intellect to produce second-order concepts, through which the intellect produces 'assent'. One of Aureol's examples for cases where first-order intentional being does NOT correspond to real objects is - tellingly - the case of dreams...

When the *esse intentionale* and the object are identical, we experience adequate and veridical understanding; when they are not - as in cases of optical illusions (a stick dipped in water; afterimages; a candle moved in a circle, etc.) - we perceive only the apparent being and not the thing 'as it is'. This - however - is the biggest flaw with Aureol's theory, and concerns precisely the question of how exactly we might in practice differentiate illusory perceptual experiences from veridical ones. There seems no obvious way to explain this, and indeed Auriol argues that it is totally possible to have an intuitive cognition of a non-existent object - and intuitive cognition after Scotus is defined as the kind of knowledge whose truthfulness we can ascertain, and usually obtains in the presence of its object(!). But Auriol's avoidance of the central problem relating to the manner in which we differentiate between erroneous and accurate intuitive cognition begs the real question: **how does the intellect verify that first-order intentions correspond to outward objects and produce the assent necessary for second-order intentions, if our act of perception is unable to bypass the intentional being (or *esse apparens*) itself to apprehend the object itself 'as such'? How can we measure the distance separating the *esse apparens* from the object if we never perceive the latter but only the former, and decide that our perceptive act can be trusted (second intention)?** This, it seems to me, crystallises the real problem - and this is also the primary objection levelled against Aureol by successive generations of later scholastics - many of them writing in England - such as Ockham, Chatton, and Wodeham...

ADD from Denery?

There is an even more extreme theory of perception that comes about as a reaction to Auriol's ideas: this can be found in the writings of Nicolas of Autrecourt in Paris - although his views are condemned, he is forced to recant, burn his books, and there is no sign that his theories ever had any wider influence. Still, they are interesting because in some sense his theory works out the extreme implications that are latent in Auriol's theory. For Auriol - as we have just seen - what is perceived is not the *res extra* itself (nor is it the species, or indeed the object *by means* of the *species*...) but an *esse apparens* produced by the senses and the intellect, which may or may not coincide with the *res*.

Autrecourt's point by contrast - broadly speaking - is that we do perceive objects directly, but we do so in ways that only convey a partial aspect of those objects. Our cognitive abilities simply determine that it is not possible for us to have full, unified and definitive apprehension of a single object at any one time. So, for instance, if we were to look at the same object - say a white circle - in two different circumstances and at two different moments, we do not in effect see the same object, because the target of the perceptual act is not the contingent *res* itself, but rather the object perceived under a particular *aspect*. Multiple acts of perception can apprehend different, and complementary aspects of an object - and in fact Autrecourt claimed that each cognitive act, even when focusing on the same *res*, has its own, unique object. We can arrive at what we assume to be a 'fuller' apprehension of the object 'as such' — through comparison of multiple acts of perception repeated in time and through inference — we can never either apprehend the object fully and definitively as it really is. Nor do we have any means to ascertain to what degree the object 'as apprehended through our act(s) of perception' diverges from the object *as such*.

This - again - implies a radically contingent understanding of knowledge - and although Autrecourt starts from the opposite assumption than Auriol (for whom we perceive apparent beings and never simple objects as such), their theories ultimately founder because of the same gap that obtains between **experience** and actual **being**.

Autrecourt goes further though, because he postulates that multiple perceptual acts can as it were be 'collated and compared', and thus become 'accretive' in some sense, enabling a continuously improved (albeit still only 'probable') understanding; but he also postulates that different perceivers, characterised by divergent cognitive abilities, will usually have subtly, but at times *fundamentally* different apprehensions of particular objects, as determined by their cognitive abilities, predispositions, and previous experiences. This - if anything - implies an even more radical degree of contingency and divergence, suggesting that not only our respective perceptual acts differ internally and across time, but that they differ from one person to another. If you and I look at the same blackbird in the same instant, we do not see the same thing.

For us this may be obvious - but to say this in the fourteenth century is explosive, and indeed Nicholas is forced to recant his views.

Auriol's *esse apparens* is rejected by Ockham - who arguably misunderstands Auriol; Ockham equally rejects the instrumental role of *species* (he follows Olivi here), on the same grounds that these notions would constitute intermediary instances between object and perceiver.

For Ockham, objects act upon sense organ directly, leaving behind a '*qualitas impressa*'. Ockham also introduces a key distinction between the *apprehensive* and the *adjudicative* operations of the cognitive powers: as in Abelard, this is designed to separate the relatively mechanical act of apprehending information (the *notae* or marks or qualities of external realities...) from the act of providing one's assent to what is apprehended, or indeed to the form of the apprehension itself as an act, which is the strictly cognitive component of the process. And while the apprehensive operation pertains to things, the adjudicative process actually pertains to mental propositions - and this is an element in Ockham's thought that leads him to develop fully-fledged theory of mental language, namely the idea that the mind functions linguistically and propositionally in its formulation of cognitive assent (a very different idea from Abelard's, but here too the underlying insight is the perceived fundamental analogy between the understanding of linguistic propositions and the cognition of *res subiectae* or 'objects').

For Adam Wodeham - who defends the existence of *species* - the object of cognition is neither the *species* nor the *esse apparens*, but a similarly elusive *Complexo Significabile*, which is defined as an

abstract but extra-mental entity signified by linguistic constructs. Here again, the focus on the *complexe significabile* suggests that the status of the mind's objects of perception is ultimately 'propositional', and thus linguistic: while it is not the proposition itself to which the mind provides 'assent' it is 'that which the proposition signifies', i.e. an external state of affairs enunciated in the proposition - the *complexe significabile*.

A final case is constituted by Nicolas Oresme : he is the one fourteenth-century figure who actually reintroduces the term *attentio* into the discussion of perception and epistemology. Oresme is also the one thinker that to my mind like Abelard, confronts head on the key problem of the overwhelmingly passive nature of the cognitive act: this is a question that had been largely implicit and submerged in the rather more technical debates on epistemology that took place after Scotus. Oresme also makes explicit another ideas that underlies many earlier discussions without being explicitly articulated, namely the idea that nay act of perception or sensation also involves a judgement - that is, an act of the will.

Oresme thus postulates that already at the stage of perception - in the internal senses - the perceiver exercises an elementary form of discursive judgement (*discursus*) through the exercise of 'discernment' (*virtus distinctiva*). This is particularly the case when the qualities in play are not the proper sensibles (such as colour), but common sensibles (such as movement). Like Abelard, Oresme insists on the need to 'decompose' sensory input (*dearticulatio*), in a process that is both sequential and in some sense discursive, turning the sensory apprehension into a series of successive instances of judgment that come about through the channeling of attention - *attentio*, although Oresme's preferred term is *advertentia*.

A further element in Oresme's system is entirely novel, and this is the role of *habitus* in directing and organising the perceptual process: crucially, Oresme invokes *habitus* in order to differentiate between human abilities, and specifically in order to explain why multiple subjects/agents would perceive a single object in very different manners - again, the same problem of 'divergent' cognitive acts that we find in Abelard, Auriol, and Autrecourt, with increasingly troubling and increasingly explicit implications in terms of the possibility of obtaining 'certain knowledge'. While generally speaking *habitus* has a positive impact on one's perceptual ability (a musician will perceive and decompose melody more easily than an ordinary person...), *habitus* can also become an obstacle, particularly where *habitus* channels false belief: in fact - and this is pretty innovative - Oresme suggests that prolonged exposure to false or superstitious narratives can compromise our ability to 'discern' the truth in perceptual acts - for instance, those repeatedly exposed to superstitious accounts about the existence of ghosts, or other fabulous and demonic creature, thereby become more inclined to delude themselves into thinking that they truly perceive such entities: *habitus* thus compromises our ability to direct attention in adequate manner to apprehend external objects truthfully - or, if you will, to 'decode' or 'interpret' reality and its underlying causes. This too it seems to me suggests a strongly 'relativistic' understanding of the phenomena of perception: again, multiple agents/perceivers looking at the self-same object or event may, quite literally, see different things... since their attention is co-determined by *habitus*.

The challenge in both cases is the question of how the subject can establish that the resulting understanding, emerging from the operation of **attention** upon an object, is in any sense 'adequate' or 'truthful'... This difficulty means that in both cases (with sensory objects as well as

linguistic propositions) we face the potential threat of 'skepticism' (in a loose, non-technical sense). All of this affectively raises the possibility that the cognition of an identical object (or an identical proposition and therefore an identical text) by multiple individuals, may be fundamentally divergent (*this, incidentally, is what Chaucer implicitly asserts in many places, for instance when he plays off Virgil's account of Dido and Aeneas with Ovid's - but also in many other, more localised instances where he highlights a divergence between the perceptual apprehension of a single object by multiple observers >> I am thinking of the Merchant's tale, where the 'distortion' of vision is literalised to the extent of making January blind; or - to return to texts - the Wife of Bath's deliberate misreading of scripture, or, not to mention Chaucer ironic-laconic citation of St Paul to the intent that 'everything that is written is written for our doctrine...'*).

While this does not make knowledge impossible (this would be radical, 'academic' skepticism), it nonetheless suggests that there is no clear way of ensuring the commonality between my understanding of a simple object, a linguistic proposition, or an extended text, and that available to another person. That is - it seems to me - quite a radical and striking suggestion, and in some ways a pretty 'modern' one (although I don't think the concept of 'modernity' is a very useful one, here and in general.). Both medieval scholastics and medieval poets seem to work out this idea. The bulk of the research on understanding how the thinking of the scholastics influences - or perhaps 'interferes with' or 'meshes with' or 'interfaces' perhaps simply 'conditions' (or not..) the thinking of the poets - remains to a very large extent to be done.